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Managing Social Innovations In Education: The Way Forward In Nigeria Education System

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ABSTRACT

The study examined social contexts and education as it relates with innovation. Social innovations seek the transformation of society through innovative solutions. These solutions not only pursue the generation of social value but also operate under criteria of economic sustainability, making a tension in their management models and resulting in the creation of social enterprises, hybrid organizations etc. societies are dynamic and evolve. There is need for transformation to take place within societies and social tools and innovations are weapons that are tangible in the transformation process. Societies operate various systems and sub-systems, of which the education system belongs to. Education is a viable and veritable tool that can be used to ameliorate the diverse issues that plague societies. Nigerian education system is faced with a mirage of challenges that have plagued the nation for decades. Innovations within the social context can help address these issues and proffer a way forward.

Keywords: Management, Education, Societies, Social Innovations,

INTRODUCTION

In every sphere of life, education is very essential. It is an all important aspect in the growth and development of any society. Education is the transmission of knowledge, idea, culture and information from one generation to another. It is also regarded as the oil that drives the wheel of the engine of any nation. No country can fully make progress without imbibing the tenets of education. Education is the bedrock on which development thrives. It is seen and regarded as the most important tool that can be used to transform a society, state or nation. For the meaningful growth and development of any society, education is widely seen as a viable instrument that can make that happen. It has been empirically proven and universally acknowledged that unless the citizens of a given country are well educated and appropriately trained, the achievements of rapid economic and social development cannot be guaranteed (Ahmad, 2013). It has been observed that education helps develop a society and propel them to greater heights. There are basically three levels of education namely; primary, secondary and tertiary. No society can sustain itself comprehensively without education and its practices.

The main purpose of education is to train individuals within a society, to prepare and qualify them for work in the economy as well as to integrate them into the society and teach them the values and morals of the society (Karim & Abdullah, 2012). It, therefore, contributes to the growth and development of an individual. Education operates within the confinement of societies. Individuals exist in societies and are educated in order to transform their societies meaningfully. Education is seen as an all important tool for

the transformation of societies. These transformations enable citizens become useful to their societies. Within societies, innovation is bound to occur.

Concept of Social Innovations

Social innovation refers to the design and implementation of new solutions that imply conceptual, process, product or organizational change, which ultimately aim to improve the welfare and wellbeing of individuals and communities. In other words, the essence of social innovation is to enact social change and address challenges in businesses and communities alike through new frameworks, services and programs. Social innovation refers to the development and implementation of new ideas and practices to address social problems and create positive change. Many educators, scholars and policymakers agree that the earlier students develop a deep understanding and a mindset conducive to innovation and sustainability, the more prepared they are to thrive in a fast-changing world (Bell, 2016). It involves creating solutions that are more effective, efficient, sustainable, or just than existing ones, often benefiting society as a whole. These innovations can range from new programs and policies to innovative organizational structures and approaches. It also aims to improve lives and address societal challenges, such as poverty, inequality, environmental degradation, and lack of access to education or healthcare. . Some international organizations have focused on measuring innovation, such as the implementation of technology in classrooms and schools (OECD 2014; OECD 2016; Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019), or in developing observatories of technological transformation in education (UNESCO, 2021), while other perspectives have focused on the governance of innovation in education (Cerna, 2014).

Social innovations, aiming to transform the way social needs are met through better-performing solutions, positively affect a wide range of social issues — including community health, education, professional working environments, social development and so many more. Social innovation is the process of developing and deploying effective solutions to challenging and often systemic social and environmental issues in support of social progress. Social innovation is not the prerogative or privilege of any organizational form or legal structure. Solutions often require the active collaboration of constituents across government, business, and the non-profit world. Social innovation refers to a new way of doing things, an innovative element in a given context. It represents a breaking away from the usual solutions offered and provides a creative response to social and economic problems that cannot be solved by the market or state. It thus improves individual and collective well-being. Social innovation is defined as a dynamic process of strategically developing and implementing inventive ideas, strategies, or interventions aimed at proactively addressing prevalent social issues and instigating positive, transformative change.

The advent of 21st century has raised an increased interest in addressing education for innovation, entrepreneurship and sustainable development even from the early school years. Conceptualizing social innovation in formal education has become a very difficult task, as there are many perspectives and types of education involved. Despite many efforts to delimit this concept, it is true that it is a field in search of common ground in understanding, identifying and integrating different types of social innovation in education

Social Innovation in the Education System

Social innovation in education involves creating and implementing novel solutions to address social issues within the education system, aiming to improve student well-being, community engagement, and societal impact. It is a student-led, action-oriented approach that encourages collaboration, problem-solving, and the development of innovative solutions to meet social needs. Excellence and values are crucial terms, which need to be taken into consideration to bring about improvements and advancement of education (Maciuk, 2013). It is important not to underestimate the importance of social innovation in education. Social progress and advancements in technology have always been closely intertwined. New technology in education and society can promote a higher quality of life, which in turn creates a community free to pursue scientific advancements. On a socioeconomic level, the impact of innovation is

far-reaching and essential for growth. That is why Maduwesi and Ofojebe (2012) maintained that the development of any nation depends to a great extent on the advancement made in their education.

Technological advancements, for example, allow social change groups to think big. With the right equipment, social programs can tackle global and local issues with improved efficiency. Productivity improves as these organizations spend less time dealing with outdated technology and more time focused on social progress. Plus, social groups can spend their money furthering their cause instead of constantly repairing old and faulty equipment. Nyanganji, Atumba and Awa (2018) noted that the World Education Forum held in Dakar in 2000, much emphasis was laid on the need to achieve education for all as well as the need to improve the quality of education. Using the latest technology to solve social issues also has a strong economic impact. As more people have a high quality of life, societies become more prosperous. Not only does the efficiency of nonprofits improve with new technology, but these organizations provide more employment opportunities that strengthen the economy. In this way, social innovation strategies give back as much as they receive and then some.

The benefits of using educational technology in the classroom, however, is backed by extensive educational research. Teachers who use technology in their lessons often notice that with regular use, their students develop stronger communication skills and engage more often in class. It also provides more self-directed activities and opportunities for personalized or differentiated education for students who need it. This is because quality education is the measurement of standard of education in comparison to other parameters that surround teaching and learning (Ishaya, 2018), which includes how learning is organized and managed, what the content of learning is, what level is achieved, what it leads to in terms of outcomes and what goes on in the learning environment. And best of all, studies suggest that a student's retention rate is highest when lessons or study sessions incorporate educational technology. School wide technological trends primarily involve solving social issues in education. Parent engagement in schools, for example, is often limited due to scheduling or transportation issues. Thanks to parent-teacher communication apps, websites, and texting programs, however, teachers have been able to bridge this gap. And because most parents prefer online communication, collaboration between families and teachers often increase with tech-based innovations. Because the vast majority of jobs require technological skills, teaching students digital literacy skills is another innovative trend in education. While the two are interconnected, digital literacy does not refer to traditional reading skills.

Digital literacy is the ability to access digital media and absorb it efficiently. Through innovations like typing skills software, interactive digital activities, and adaptive learning algorithms, educators can simultaneously teach their students academic and digital literacy skills. By pairing their curriculum with social innovation, schools can make an impactful investment in child education.

Challenges to Quality Education Delivery in Nigeria

Nigeria education system is faced with a mirage of challenges and setbacks. These challenges which threaten educational systems, thereby hindering the provision of quality education in Nigeria, include: inadequate funding, poor supervision, non-recruitments of qualified teachers, inadequate remuneration, non-personnel development and training of teachers, poor educational administration and inadequate curriculum provision, amongst others. Nyakundi (2012) highlighted the following challenges plaguing quality education delivery in Nigeria:

Inadequate Funding

For any project to succeed, the issue of fund cannot be ruled out. Education requires huge capital investment to carryout educational projects for quality education. Nyanganji, Atumba and Awu (2018) noted that the challenge may not be with the actual funding, but the proper utilization of the meager funds in an era of economic difficulties to offer desired quality education to the learners. Emefo (2009) noted that adequate fund is needed for the provision of facilities for learning like classrooms, laboratories, power supply, equipment, libraries, toilets among others for quality education. Unfortunately, some schools in Nigeria do not have modern laboratories and where these laboratories are found, they are either

not equipped properly or the teachers to handle the equipment for learning are not competent. This is a serious challenge to the provision of quality education.

Poor Supervision

Supervision is an essential ingredient of success in any project. It can be likened to follow up of activities in any project if success will be ensured. In education project, the issue of follow up (supervision) cannot be overlooked if quality is expected to be achieved. Supervision is an art of overseeing the activities of teachers and other educational workers in a school system to ensure that they conform to generally accepted principles and practices of education and the stipulated policies and guidelines of education authority (Ogunu, 2008). When this is critically examined, it portrays Nigeria's areas of lapses in influencing teaching practice. Government carry out their responsibility of providing pre-service and in-service training for teachers as well as distribution of textbooks for teachers' use in the classroom but the aspect of checking the teachers to ensure that they do what they are expected to do according to the laid down rules that are supposed to guide them and to ensure that the books distributed are utilized in teaching for desired quality is not there. Unfortunately, the government are not doing much as far as this aspect is concerned, despite the fact that there are some educational bodies like National Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC), SPEB and other educational agencies, still the aspect of proper monitoring and ensuring compliance are farfetched. This is a challenge to the provision of quality education in schools.

Non-Recruitment of Qualified Teachers

Another challenge facing educational system in Nigeria that deprives it from providing quality education is non-recruitment of qualified teachers. The Federal Government of Nigeria (FRN, 2012) states that no educational system can rise above the quality of its teachers. For any educational system to achieve success in quality, teachers competency and qualification cannot be neglected This is because, the teacher is the implementer of the curriculum. Unfortunately, as observed by Nyanganji, Atumba and Awu (2018), several professionally unqualified teachers still find their ways to the system. This is as a result of porous nature of the recruitment exercise.

Inadequate Remuneration

Nyakundi (2012) observed that inadequate remuneration of teachers poses as challenge to quality of education in Nigeria. According to the author, a good number of teachers appear not to be motivated. These teachers do not put in their best in the classroom. Remuneration influence teachers' motivation to work and hardwork result to quality in education. Ofojebe and Ezugoh (2010) revealed that salary remuneration, lack of motivational strategies like staff training and development, promotion, improved working conditions and several related factors are barriers toward achieving quality assurance in the educational system. Regular payment of teacher's salaries, allowances and other accrue benefits are very significant areas in the process of education that needs urgent attention. Good rewards yield and begets hard work. Teachers need appropriate remuneration (Emefo, 2009).For there to be quality in any educational system, teachers should be remunerated to ensure quality in their delivery. Inadequate remuneration can kill teachers' motivation to put in their best for quality education.

Non-Personnel Development and Training of Teachers

Non-personnel development and training of teachers pose a challenge to quality education. Some recommended training for teachers like in-service training, seminars, workshops and conferences are meant to improve teachers' quality in lesson delivery are hardly provided in Nigeria. In-service training also creates an avenue for those who are already engaged in teaching who lack professional qualification to register and update their knowledge (Emefo, 2009). To keep teachers off from participating in these trainings, workshops and conferences with the excuse of shortage of teachers will be affecting the attainment of quality education because they will not be acquainted with some innovations in educational system that will enhance quality in education.

Poor Educational Administration

Poor educational administration is another issue that can affect quality delivery in the educational system. Educational administration is the process of coordinating men and materials in educational setup for

effective and functional teaching and learning in the school, towards achieving quality in education. Unfortunately, those that are found in these management positions in schools are neither trained in these positions nor adequately trained. They get there either by promotion or through political connections. This incidence of improper coordination of men and resources in educational setting towards achieving the goal of education is therefore a challenge in achieving quality in our educational system.

Inadequate Curriculum Provision

Curriculum has to do with all the learning experience which a child acquires under the guidance of the school. The curriculum of a nation is supposed to be in line with meeting the educational goals of the nation. The need of the society and the learner has to be achieved through the implementation of adequate curriculum that will address these needs. For instance, in this era of knowledge explosion on technology and skills, the curriculum should gear towards technology driven education that can enhance the acquisition of skills by the learner. This means that curriculum should always be reviewed to address the fast pace of global changes. It is worthy of note that before curriculum is reviewed, there may be emerging issues which may have begun to take their toll on the system and therefore, teachers may feel obliged to address them through education (Nyanganji, Atumba and Awu, 2019). Such issues include HIV/AIDS, population theme, gender equity, information technology and a host of others were already being addressed by the teachers long before adequate provision was made for them in the written curriculum. The inability to reverse the curriculum when due in other to meet the needs of the society and learners is a challenge to achieving quality in the education system. Nyanganji, Atumba and Awu (2019) therefore remarked that regularity, relevance and review should be the watchwords of policy developers in view of the fast pace global changes.

Social Innovations in Addressing Challenges faced in the Nigerian Education System

Social innovation is often an effort of mental creativity which involves fluency and flexibility from a wide range of disciplines. The act of social innovation in a sector is mostly connected with diverse disciplines within the society. It is the process of developing and deploying effective solutions to challenging and often systemic social and environmental issues in support of social progress. The Nigerian education system is one that has been met with a plethora of challenges and setbacks. The following social innovations can be used in addressing some of these challenges as follow:

Alternative sources of funding

Social innovations involve deploying effective solutions to societal problems. In the Nigerian educational system, funding is a huge problem facing stakeholders and individuals. Lack of adequate funding has made the education system within the country look like a child's play and unattractive to external bodies. Funding is an integral part of the school system. Finance is an essential part of the organization system and is referred to as a financial resource. It is very instrumental in the running of activities in any institution. The National Policy on Education, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013:47) stated that "education is a capital-intensive social service, which requires adequate financial provisions from all tiers of government for successful implementation of educational programmes". This proclamation affirms that educational programmes and goals cannot be achieved if adequate funding is not provided. Finance is defined as the management of money and includes activities such as investing, borrowing, lending, budgeting, saving and forecasting. Schools can look out for alternative sources of funding such as sale of school agricultural products, alumni, social programmes, renting of school facilities, school / investors collaboration amongst others.

Proceeds from school farm can also be sold in canteens and restaurants for revenue making. Farm products are end products harvested from the farms where farming occurred and took place. The essence of cultivating crops is either to consume them or to sell them to generate profit. Most schools have boarding facilities and most of the food given to students are derived or gotten from the school farm. It is worthy to note that farm products harvested in schools are in most cases, harvested in large quantities and most schools sell these products to the public.

Social programmes proceed can also be a source of alternative revenue. Here, social programs are organized for other schools to partake and engage in, thus creating funds for the school. When other school students engage in pageantry competitions, cultural dance competitions and others, they bring in money for the schools. Ezeugbor and Obi (2015) opined that this is a way of generating revenue internally in educational institutions. Renting school facilities is also a critical and essential alternative source of generating funds and revenues in universities. Jacobson (2013) opined income can be generated through employing existing resources more effectively. Gebreyes (2015) reiterated that schools have considerable opportunities to exploit their facilities for generating revenue.

Use of ICT in schools

ICT is an integral part of social innovation as it depicts the use of technology in proffering solutions to societal issues. The use of electronic and technological tools in the school system will help tackle slow pace in the handling of administrative jobs. The use of computers, projectors, electronic boards, internet services etc, are essential and important in the school system to minimize wastages and enhance educational activities. Also, it can be helpful to human resource personnel in schools. The use of electronic human resource management in handling administrative tasks is also very paramount. Poisat (2017) opined that using E-HRM, managers can easily access any relevant information, make decisions and communicate with others without referring to the human resource department each time. Therefore, succinctly put, Electronic Human Resource Management (E-HRM) is a concept which involves the use of Web-based technologies for providing the services regarding the human resource management in the organization. E-HRM can also help HR professionals focus on strategic planning and growth by freeing them from intermediary functions. Therefore, E-HRM can be the integration between human resources management, and information technology, through mainly the use of web-based applications in human resources management. The purpose of this web-based tool is to support HR professionals in performing their HR tasks, and to support managers and employees performing their HR tasks.

Collaborative Learning

Collaboration refers to the joint intellectual efforts by everyone within an organization in achieving a goal. In schools, it refers to the joint efforts put together by both principals, students and teachers in order to achieve school goals. Here, everyone within the school system put their hands together to accomplish a task and do not leave it in the hands of one person. Students that collaborate together work in group of two or more, mutually searching for understanding, solutions, meanings or creating a product. Collaborating with one another means co-operating together in schools to work as a team and group to solve issues and proffer solutions to educational problems. One good thing about effective collaboration is that it helps leads to cooperation and build relationships. The principle of schools collaborating to improve is one that has seen growing interest in recent years (Mujis, 2015). Besides the traditional method of lecture method of teaching and doing things alone, social innovations suggest collaborating with one another in order to brainstorm, think critically and help solve group tasks. Encouraging students to work together on projects and assignments can foster teamwork, communication skills, and a deeper understanding of the material. This can involve using online platforms, group projects, and peer-to-peer learning.

Design Thinking

Using a human-centered approach to problem-solving can help students develop critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills. This can involve identifying challenges, brainstorming solutions, and prototyping and testing ideas.

Innovative Use of Technology

Integrating technology into education can enhance engagement, provide access to resources, and improve learning outcomes. This can include using educational apps, online learning platforms, and AI-powered tools. E-teaching media also comes to play here as well. The use of e-teaching media such as zoom, electronic books, recorded audio, computers will help facilitate the teaching and learning process.

Blended Learning

Combining online and in-person learning can provide flexibility, personalize the learning experience, and make education more accessible. This can involve using online resources, virtual classrooms, and hybrid learning models. It is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with physical place-based classroom methods. This is very effective for knowledge retention and to enhance the critical thinking of students outside the classroom, before entering the classroom for lectures.

Social innovations help manage societal issues, as well as proffer solutions to them. Societies over the years have faced several challenges and this has impeded the growth and development of these societies. Bringing in creative innovations to education will help reduce or manage educational problems which will go a long way in facilitating the teaching and learning process.

CONCLUSION

Education is very important and transcends from generation to generation. Societies are involved in social activities which pave the way for sustainable growth and development. Within educational institutions in these societies, schools face challenges and it is essential for innovations to be implemented in order to address them for optimal societal change. Applying certain social innovations will go a long way in solving some of these educational issues.

Suggestions

1. Educational stakeholders in Nigeria should adopt the use of ICT in schools and ensure that they are applied within all educational institutions, both at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels.
2. School and educational administrators should encourage collaborative learning among students
3. Educational institutions should look critically at ways they can source for alternative funding.

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